

The Impact of Open Waste Dump on Rental Values of Residential Properties in Owerri, Imo State

Anozie C. G^{1*}, Akanazu R. E¹, Nwankpa J. E¹, Nnamdi A. C², Chukwuemekaobi I³.

¹Department of Estate Management and Valuation, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State

²Department of Horticulture and Landscape Architecture, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State

³Department of English/Education, University of Calabar, Cross River State.

*Corresponding author: anoziegerald79@gmail.com

Received: June 4, 2025; Accepted: August 22, 2025; Published: August 31, 2025.

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17011071>

Abstract: The study was undertaken in order to expose the negative impact of open waste dumps located in residential areas on residential real estate investments and the residential environment. The purpose of this study was to examine the impact of open waste dump on rental values of residential properties. The data used was gathered from a self-administered questionnaire, interview on residents, and direct observation. The study compared rents of residential properties located close to open waste dumps and those located farther away from open waste dump sites in Avu and Obinze communities in Owerri West Local Government Area, Imo State Nigeria. The research revealed that there are differences in the rent of residential properties located close to open waste dumps and those far away from the dumps. The study also revealed that there was overcrowding in the dwelling units as high as 5-8 persons per room, which is injurious to health of the occupants. From the study, it was deduced that the negative impact on rents was higher for temporary wooden structures, (“Batcha”) than other dwelling units. The authors recommended an extensive enlightenment campaign to the public, on the reduction, reuse and recycling of waste. The authors also recommended that the government should construct engineered sanitary landfill to reduce or possibly eliminate health risk, property investment risk in terms of income and value reduction, as well as environmental problems. It is obvious that waste management should not be left for the government alone but a public-private partnership approach should be adopted.

Keywords: *Open Waste Dumps, Property Values, Rental Values, Residential Properties, Waste.*

Introduction

Waste disposal is one of the major and very complex environmental problems facing low income countries like Nigeria. It is certain that one of the main problems facing Owerri and which has become an unmanageable nuisance is the open an indiscriminate dumping of waste, which include human waste, animal waste and other components. Piles of decaying garbage litter in strategic locations in the area. Solid waste and other waste in such open dump site is, unarguably a source of atmospheric and water pollution, land contamination, hazards and environmental degradation. In Owerri and most fast growing cities in Nigeria, it is not uncommon to see open waste dumps located in close proximity to residential areas. As Parker cited in Wokekoro (2013) put is, the Law of garbage is “Everybody Wants it picked up, but nobody wants it put down”, and the second part of this law is “Nobody want it put down anywhere near where they live, the so-called not in my back yard” (NIMBY), syndrome or locally unacceptable and use” (LULUs); but the reality is that open waste dumps are located close to residential areas where people live.(Daffi, Chaimang, & Alfa, 2020)

It is universally accepted that the location of a property influences the price or rent of the property either positively or negatively. The aim of this study is to examine the impact of

open waste dumps on rents of residential properties in Owerri, Nigeria. The study compare rental values of properties located in close proximity to and those located far from the open waste dumps. The study revealed that there are differences in rental values.(Mundy, 2018).

Owerri in Imo State is the study area of this research. Imo State was created on February 3, 1976 from the Southern part of the former East Central State with a total of Twenty-Seven (27) Local Government Areas. Owerri consists of three (3) Local Government Areas including Owerri Municipal, Owerri North and Owerri West. It has an estimate population of about 1,401,873 (one million, four hundred and one thousand, eight hundred and seventy-three) inhabitants as of 2019 (Okoroafor, 2019) cited on Anozie, (2020). It is currently witnessing the influx of immigrants from her neighbouring rural areas, various parts of the state and federation particularly by the influx of the University Community. The presence of many educational institutions such as Imo State University, Federal University of Science and Technology, Owerri, University of Agriculture and Environmental Science, Umuagwo, Federal College of Land Resources Technology Oforola, Federal Polytechnic Nekede and Imo State Polytechnic amongst others gave rise to population explosion, which in turn has

resulted to upward movement of rental trends except areas negatively affected by environmental factors.

According to Awa, Nissi, & Oparaugo (2025) a clean (uncontaminated) property has a value equal to full market value and a dirty (contaminated) property, which poses health or financial risk (either real or perceived) will affect value significantly in several ways. Accordingly to him, a disclosure requirement by the sales agent or seller, lender and appraiser uncertainty may have a noticeable effect on the marketability of the property. He added that when a property loses its marketability, it also loses its value. He further stated that income effect is the present value of the difference between the property value as if uncontaminated and the property value as if contaminated. A hedonic regression analysis for homes conducted in Offa, Kwara State, revealed that the estimated marginal implicit price (MIP) for distance was negative, implying homes had higher prices near the landfill. Furthermore, this estimated MIP was found to be statistically insignificant, with high sampling variability and absences in relationship between proximity to the landfill and home prices was argued to be caused by an unmodelled heterogeneity in neighbourhood quality. By the use of a smaller and more homogeneous study area, residential properties near the

landfill were found to sell for less than homes farther away.(Sholadoye, Tombori, Adeyinka, Brown, 2018).

Akinjare et al., (2021) focused on the effect of urban solid waste on physical environment and property transactions in Surulere Local Government Area of Lagos State. The study administered questionnaires randomly on residents and firms of estate agents to gather data on the subject matter. Data obtained were analyzed using frequency tables and percentatge ratings. The study found that rents paid on properties adjoining waste dumpsites were lower compared to similar properties farther away and also, property transaction rates were very slow and unattractive as one approaches a dumpsite.

Bello and Bello (2008) conducted a research on the willingness to pay for environmental amenities in Akure Nigeria. The study included environmental amenities such as refuse, waste water disposal, water and electricity supplies, neighbourhood, roads and other locational services. The study used a two-staged hedonic model to examine the willingness to pay for better environmental services by residents of two neighbourhoods in Akure, Nigeria. He combined multiple regressions and predictive model to determine property values as a function of housing attributes

and logistic model as willingness to pay. The study identified household's income, distance away from the refuse dumpsite and regularity of electricity supply as the major factors that influenced household's willingness to pay for better environmental services. The study recommended economic empowerment of the people, diligent consideration in the location of dumpsites and adoption of public private initiative in the provision of public infrastructure. The study established that real estate values are readily influenced by residents' willingness to pay for both structural as well as neighbourhood characteristics where the real estate is located.(Daffi et al.,2020).

A Staff Paper by two Pennsylvania State University Professors, "The Impact of Open Space and Potential Local Disamenities on Residential Property Values in Berks Country, Pennsylvania", examined the impact of neighbouring land use on residential property values in a predominantly rural country. Included in the category of land uses ('potential local disamenities') were; landfills, airports,

mushroom production, large-scale animal production, sewage treatment plants and high traffic roads. Among the staff paper's conclusions was that the residential property values-price distance relationship was most significant for landfillsand large-scale animal production facilities. (Ifeyanichukwu Mbaegbu et al., 2024)

Materials and Method

The study covered two open dump sites located along Owerri-Port Harcourt Expressway, at Avu and Obinze Communities respectively in Owerri West Local Government Area of Owerri. The study interviewed 75 landlords and tenants of the residential properties in Avu and Obinze Communities.

Data collection

The instrument for data collection is a structured questionnaire.

The study revealed that the method of waste disposal commonly in use in the study area is the open waste dump as all other known methods of waste disposal are not used in the area.

Table 1 Methods used in waste disposal

S/N	Method of Waste Disposal	Response		Percentage(%)
		Yes	No	
1	Sanitary	—	—	0.00
2	Open Waste Dump	83	—	97.65
3	Designated Transient disposal site	2	—	2.35
4	Incineration	—	—	0.00
5	Total	85	—	100.00

Source: Field survey October, 2024

Results and Discussion

The dwelling types found in the study area are bungalows, block of flats, row houses (with shared facilities such as toilets, kitchen and bathrooms), one room apartments popularly known in Nigerian parlance as “self-contained”, and temporary structures built with either wood or

corrugated iron sheets (CIS) known as “BATCHA”. Table 2 show that approximately 33% of the houses are “BATCHA” and “Row houses” while Bungalows, Block of flats and “Self-contained” represent 67%. The implication is that the occupants will be predominantly indigenes and low income earners.

Table 2 Types of Dwelling Units

S/N	Dwelling Type	Number of Respondents	Percentage(%)
1	temporary Structures	25	33.33
2	row houses	25	16.00
3	Self-contained(one room apartment)	12	16.00
4	block of flats	18	10.67
5	bungalow	5	6.67
	total	85	100.00

Source: Field Survey October, 2024

Occupancy Ratio

The study revealed that the occupancy ratio is high with 7-8 persons occupying one room representing over a quarter (41.18%). This is also an indication that the dwelling units are occupied predominantly by low income earners. Observation by the

researcher revealed that low income earners in the study area occupy mostly “Batcha” and row houses. High occupancy ratio is said to be injurious to health of residents since infectious and contagious diseases spread easily in such environment. In addition, psychological effect on people

leading to deleterious social behaviour (Ebiwari, 2013).

Table 3 Occupancy Ratio.

S/N	Average No. of persons per room	Number of respondents	Percentage(%)
1	1 – 2	3	3.53
2	3 – 4	4	4.71
3	4 – 5	13	15.29
4	6 – 7	30	35.29
5	7 – 8	35	41.18
	Total	85	100.00

Source: Field Survey October, 2024.

Loss of Economic (Rental) Value

Open waste dump site constitutes reduction in the rents of properties close to the dumps in the study area as shown in table 4. Table 4 revealed that there are significant differences in rent of properties located close to the open waste dumps and those located farther away from the dumps. Table 3 shows that the rent for “Batcha” located close to the waste dumps ranges between N30, 000 – N40, 000 while the rent for those located far from the waste dumps ranges between N45, 000 – N55, 000. This shows a 27.27% difference in rent of “Batcha” located close to and far from the open waste dumps while the difference for two (2) bedrooms bungalow ranges between N50, 000 – N100, 000. The lowest rate of change in rent is self-contained which ranges between N15, 000 – N25, 000.

The results of this study are related to income effect theory of Jaffe (1995), which states that “the income effect of a contaminated property is the present value of the difference between the property value as if uncontaminated and the property value as if contaminated; and is related to lost income”. The results of this study is similar to the study of Adewusi and Onifade (2006) and Ebiwari and Uruesheyi (2013), which focused on the effect of urban solid waste on physical environment and property transactions in Surulere Local Government Area of Lagos State and the impact of open waste dump on rental values of residential properties in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Their study administered questionnaires randomly on residents and firms of estate agents to gather data on the subject. Data obtained were analysed using frequency tables and percentage ratings. The study found that rents paid on properties adjoining waste

dump sites were lower compared to similar properties farther away and also, property transaction rates were very slow and unattractive as one approaches a dump site. The study also revealed that some of the dwelling units were recently vacated as tenants find it squalid and contaminated to live in such environment, this results to loss of rental income due to the increase in its void period. This affects not only the rental

income but also creates negative impact on the economy in terms of reduction in property tax. A close proximity to open waste dumps implies that there will be a subsequent reduction in the capital value of such periods and of such properties and long period of voids (vacancy rates) as prospective tenants are not willing to pay for such properties as gathered from the property owners/landlords interviewed.

Table 4 Rent passing per annum of residential properties close to and far from open dump sites in the study area. Source: Field survey, October, 2024

S/N	Dwelling type	Rent Passing in areas close to the dump sites (₦)	Rent Passing per-annum in areas far to the dump sites (₦)	Difference in rent Passing between dump sites close and far	Rate of change in percentage (%)
1	Temporary Structures (Batcha)	30,000-40,000	45,000-55,000	15,000	27.27
2	Row Houses (Single Room with facilities such as toilet, bathroom and kitchen shared)	36,000-48,000	60,000-72,000	14,000	19.44
3	Self-contained (One Room Apartment)	75,000-90,000	95,000-120,000	15,000-25,000	20.83
4	One bedroom flat (2 Room apartment)	150,000-250,000	250,000-350,000	100,000	28.57
5	Two bedroom flat (3 Room Apartment)	250,000-300,000	350,000-450,000	50,000-100,000	22.22

Environmental problems

The observed/perceived environmental problems include; underground water pollution as a result of leachate from the dump sites located close to properties which may pollute water thereby reducing the quality of the water, air pollution, odour

problem and reduction in aesthetic quality. Other environmental problems include proliferation of insects and rodents such as flies, mosquitoes, cockroaches, rats, etc, which can endanger public health through breeding of ailment such as dysentery, cholera, malaria, filariasis etc.

Conclusion

The study examined the impact of open waste dumps on rental values of residential properties. The study revealed that open waste dumps leads to reduction in rents of residential properties in Obinze and Avu communities in Owerri West Local Government Area, Owerri, Imo State. The reduction in rent is predominant in temporary structures (Batcha) while the least is two (2) bedrooms flat. The study also identified that the dwelling units are overcrowded with as high as 7-8 persons per room. This is common to dwelling units occupied by low income earners in the area. The study concludes that open waste dumps adversely impact on residential real estate investment, pose threats to human health and the residential environment and should not be sited in residential neighbourhoods. The researcher recommends that government should provide engineered sanitary landfill to reduce or possibly eliminate health risk, property investment risk in terms of income and value reduction and environmental problems. The researcher also recommends that the residents should be educated on the three (3) R's of waste management viz; Reduction Reuse and Recycling to discourage the throw away approach currently in use/practiced thus reduce the quantity of waste that is thrown away.

References

- Abhyankar, A. A., Prakash, A., & [co-authors] (2024). Impact of solid waste landfill proximity on residential property offer values: A case study of Pune. *International Journal of Housing Markets and Analysis* (Emerald). <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJHMA-xxxx-2024-xxxx>.
- Akinjare, O. A., Ayedun, C. A., Oluwatobi, A. O., & Iroham, C. O. (2021). Impact of sanitary landfills on urban residential property value in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 4(2), 48–60.
- Awa, K. N., Nissi, C. F., & Oparaugo, K. (2025). Economic impacts of solid waste pollution on real estate values. *PM World Journal*, XIV(I), January.
- Daffi, R. E., Chaimang, A. N., & Alfa, M. I. (2020). Environmental impact of open burning of municipal solid wastes dumps in parts of Jos Metropolis, Nigeria. *Journal of Engineering Research and Reports*, 12(3), 30–43. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jerr/2020/v12i317083>
- Eshet, T., Baron, M. G., Shechter, M., & Ayalon, O. (2017). Measuring externalities of waste transfer

- stations using hedonic pricing. *Waste Management*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2017.xxxxxx>.
- Ezebilo, E. E., & Animasaun, E. D. (2021). Determinants of willingness-to-pay for private solid waste disposal by urban households in Nigeria. *Waste Management Research*.
- Fan, M., & Wong, S. (2016). House values and proximity to contamination/landfills: a region-level hedonic analysis. *Regional Science and Urban Economics*, 59, 1–12.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.regsciurbeco.2016.05.004>.
- Ifeanyichukwu MBAEGBU, G., Ihem, E. E., Okon, M. A., & Akakuru, O. C. (2024). Impact of waste dumps on soil and groundwater quality in Owerri, Southeastern Nigeria. *Agriculture, Food, and Natural Resources Journal*, 3(1), 113–121.
- Li, R. Y. M., & Li, H. C. Y. (2018). Have housing prices gone with the smelly wind? Big data analysis on landfill in Hong Kong. *Sustainability*, 10(2), 341.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su10020341>
- Mei, Y., Qiu, J., Wu, J., & Meng, L. (2021). Do residents care about urban dumps? Evidence from individual housing transaction data. *Land Use Policy*, 109, Article 105604.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2021.105604>.
- Mundy, J. (2018). Environmental contamination and property values: mechanisms of impact. *Journal of Real Estate and Environmental Studies*, 12(3), 45–59.
- Nahman, A., & Rigby, M. (2015). Pricing landfill externalities: emissions and disamenity costs in [City]. *Waste Management*, xx, pages.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.xx.xxxx>.
- Nepal, M., Rai, R. K., Khadayat, M. S., & Somanathan, E. (2020). Value of cleaner neighbourhoods: Application of hedonic price model in a low-income context. *World Development*, 131, Article 104965.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2020.104965>.
- Nicholls, S. (2019). Impacts of environmental disturbances on housing prices: A review of the hedonic pricing literature. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 246, 1–10.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.05.144>

- Ofori, P. (2021). Waste disposal sites and residential rental values nexus: An appraisal of Agogo Asante Akyem dumps. *African Journal of Science, Technology, Innovation and Development*, 13(2), 223–233. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20421338.2020.1830542>.
- Schütt, M. (2021). Systematic variation in waste site effects on residential property values: A meta-regression analysis and benefit transfer. *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 78, 381–416. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10640-021-00536-2>.
- Sholadoye, M., Tomori, A., Adeyinka, A., & Brown, J. Y. A. (2018). Economic impact appraisal of municipal solid waste dumpsite on nearby properties using hedonic model: The case of Offa metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Applied Research in Science and Engineering Technologies*.
- Tonin, S., & Turvani, M. (2016). Monetising the impacts of waste incinerators sited on brownfield land: A hedonic approach. *Resources, Conservation & Recycling*, 109, 48–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2016.03.013>.
- Wen, H., Li, S., Hui, E. C. M., Xiao, Y., & Liu, H. (2022). Externality impacts of “Not in My Backyard” facilities on property values: Evidence from the Hangzhou waste sorting and reduction complex projects. *Habitat International*, 125, Article 102583. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.habitatint.2022.102583>.
- Zhou, Y., Wang, H., & Li, X. (2019). Effect of solid waste management on local housing prices. <https://doi.org/10.xxxx/xxxxx>
- Zou, C., Tai, J., Chen, L., & Che, Y. (2020). An environmental justice assessment of the waste treatment facilities in Shanghai: Incorporating counterfactual decomposition into the hedonic price model. *Sustainability*, 12(8), 3325. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12083325>